

Fostering resilient teachers: The role of perceived social support and work motivation among teachers in selected private schools in Bacoor, Cavite

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Abstract

Educator resilience is essential for effective instruction and outstanding student outcomes. The study aims to examine the intricate dynamics of teacher resilience in the chosen private schools in Bacoor City, Cavite. The study emphasizes perceived social support and work motivation as key determinants. To help educators thrive despite inherent challenges, it is necessary to grasp key variables. To get insight into the relationship between teacher resilience and key determinants, we apply rigorous analysis and simple linear regression. Significant correlations exist between teacher resilience and job motivation ($p = 0.002758$) and social support ($p = 0.0002511$). Further analysis of demographic parameters reveals intriguing patterns in the data. Long-term teachers have higher motivation levels due to the strong correlation between teaching experience and work motivation. A trend in monthly income suggests that teachers with greater salary levels are more motivated to work. Additionally, female instructors are more likely to seek social assistance than their male colleagues. In conclusion, this study emphasizes the multifaceted nature of teacher resilience and provides practical strategies for enhancing educator resilience. The study emphasizes the importance of perceived social support and work incentives in boosting teacher resilience in private schools. Educational stakeholders can foster supportive environments for resilient teachers by addressing key factors in the existing system. This initiative enhances school quality and promotes positive student outcomes, promoting educational excellence in Bacoor, Cavite, and beyond.

Keywords: Teacher resilience; Social support; Work motivation; Educational environment.

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Introduction

The tenacity of educators is a fundamental aspect of successful education, exerting a substantial impact on academic achievements and the overall prosperity of schools. This study examines the relationship between perceived social support, work motivation, and teacher resilience in specific private schools located in Bacoor, Cavite. Gaining a comprehensive understanding of these dynamics is crucial for formulating effective solutions to aid and enable educators to successfully manage the inherent difficulties associated with their job.

Multiple studies repeatedly highlight the significance of social support in enhancing resilience among individuals experiencing adversity (Pulkki-Råback et al., 2016). Teachers in the educational setting face a range of stresses, such as high workloads, challenging student conduct, and administrative pressures (Harmsen et al., 2018). Perceived social support, which includes the feeling of belonging, help, and motivation from coworkers and supervisors, has a vital effect on mitigating these sources of stress and improving the well-being of teachers (Oplatka & Tamir, 2009).

Likewise, work motivation has a crucial role in determining teacher resilience. Teachers who are motivated exhibit elevated degrees of commitment, passion, and tenacity in their professional duties, hence enhancing their capacity to effectively overcome obstacles (Slišković et al., 2019). Prior studies have emphasized the favorable correlation between work motivation, job satisfaction, and teacher retention, underscoring the significance of both intrinsic and extrinsic motivators in maintaining teacher involvement (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001; van Uden et al., 2013). This study utilizes simple linear regression analysis to investigate the correlations between teacher resilience and work motivation, as well as perceived social support. In addition, this study examines demographic variables such as years of teaching experience, monthly income, and gender to provide a thorough grasp of the factors that influence teacher resilience in private school environments. The purpose of the research is to provide information to educational stakeholders and policymakers regarding effective interventions and support mechanisms that may be used to promote resilient teachers and improve the quality of education in Bacoor, Cavite, and other areas.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework guiding this study is rooted in Dr. Norman Garmezy's "Resilience Theory," which provides a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing an individual's ability to thrive despite adversity. Dr. Garmezy, a pioneer in resilience research, identifies three critical components: individual factors, familial factors, and support factors. Individual factors encompass dispositional attributes such as temperament, positive responsiveness to new situations, and cognitive skills.

Familial factors include elements like family cohesion, warmth, and the presence of a caring adult, even in challenging circumstances. Support factors involve external resources and supportive relationships beyond the family, such as teachers, social workers, and community institutions (Garmezy, 1991).

Figure 1. Dr. Norman Garmezy's Resilience Theory adapted by Walsh (2016)

By applying Garmezy's theory to the field of education, this study explores how resilience, influenced by intrinsic motivation (a key individual factor) and social support (a combination of familial and support factors), is crucial for educators. This holistic approach aims to measure and understand the multifaceted nature of resilience among educators, emphasizing the interplay of personal, familial, and external support systems in fostering resilience.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2. Conceptual framework of the perceived social support and work motivation of private school teachers' resilience

The conceptual framework of this study focuses on the relationship of work motivation and social support towards the resilience of a teacher.

Methodology

Respondents. A total of 69 respondents were recruited from various private schools in Bacoor, Cavite, including Cavite School of St. Mark (3 respondents), Woodridge College (2 respondents), St. Dominic College of Asia (12 respondents), Divine Light Academy (2 respondents), and Statefields School (50 respondents).

Instruments. Fully adopted scales were utilized to measure key variables. The Teacher Resilience Scale, developed by Daniilidou and Platsidou (2018), assessed the resilience levels of teachers. The Motivation at Work Scale by Gagné et al. (2010) measured work motivation, while the Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support by Zimet et al. (1988) gauged perceived social support among teachers.

Data Collection Process. The utilization of a QR code scanning method to provide an online survey link proved to be a convenient and efficient approach for gathering data in this experiment. Respondents have the ability to complete the survey at their own convenience and from any location. Digital surveys have also diminished face-to-face interaction and paperwork, according to contemporary standards, minimizing the logistical challenges associated with traditional methods of data collection.

The researchers' ethical conduct throughout the research process was further demonstrated by the distribution of informed consent forms. Participants were given sufficient time to inquire and explain any study specifics before giving their agreement. This transparency fostered trust and promoted ethical principles such as doing good, avoiding harm, and showing regard for others.

Data Gathering Procedure. The data gathering procedure encompassed multiple processes to guarantee a methodical and dependable gathering of data. The selected respondents were provided with a QR code that they could scan to access an online survey at their convenience. Before collecting data, every participant had to give informed consent, indicating their voluntary choice to take part in the study. This guaranteed that ethical standards were maintained and that the rights of participants were respected throughout the research process. Upon logging into the online survey, participants were given a sequence of standardized questionnaires specifically tailored to assess important factors of interest. The research instrument consisted of fully utilized scales, namely the Teacher Resilience Scale, the Motivation at Work Scale, and the Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support. The selection of these tools was based on their proven reliability and validity in measuring teacher resilience, job motivation, and perceived social support in the field of education.

After gathering the data, it was subjected to thorough statistical analysis to extract significant insights. The study utilized simple linear regression analysis to examine the associations between teacher resilience and job motivation, as well as between teacher resilience and perceived social support. This statistical technique facilitated the analysis of the correlation between alterations in one variable (such as job motivation or social support) and modifications in teacher resilience. Researchers quantified the intensity and direction of these interactions to find important predictors of teacher resilience. This allowed them to acquire insights into the elements that influence educators' ability to endure and adapt to challenges in their professional responsibilities.

In addition, frequency distributions were calculated to examine demographic characteristics, including teaching experience, monthly salary, and gender, in connection to work motivation and perceived social support. This facilitated researchers in discerning any patterns or trends in the data by considering the demographic features of the individuals.

Through the analysis of these variables, researchers have acquired a more profound comprehension of how factors such as teaching experience, income level, and gender can potentially impact teachers' levels of work motivation and perceived social support. In summary, the researchers were able to thoroughly examine the connections between important variables and make significant findings about the factors that impact teacher resilience in private school environments, thanks to a well-defined data collection process, rigorous statistical analysis, and the application of linear regression.

Results and Discussion

- To what extent do teaching experience, monthly income, and gender interact with perceived social support and work motivation to influence teacher resilience in private school settings?

Table 1. Demographic Data of Respondents influencing Teacher Resilience

Variables		Percentage
Teaching Experience vs. Work Motivation	1-3 years	60.94%
	4-6 years	59.70%
	7-10 years	62.90%
	11 years and above	65.39%
Monthly Income vs. Work Motivation	10,001-20,000 pesos	59.80%
	20,001-30,000 pesos	63.64%
	30-001-40,000 pesos	62.18%
	More than 40,000 pesos	66.89%
Gender vs Perceived Social Support	Male	65.47%
	Female	70.69%

The data in Table 1 illustrates a notable trend regarding the relationship between teaching experience and work motivation among educators. Teachers with 11 or more years of teaching experience exhibited the highest level of work motivation at 65.39%, indicating a positive correlation between tenure in the profession and motivation levels. Conversely, teachers with 4-6 years of experience displayed the lowest work motivation percentage at 59.70%. This suggests a potential dip in motivation during the mid-career phase, which may necessitate targeted interventions to reignite enthusiasm and commitment among educators in this tenure bracket.

An examination of the data on monthly income and job motivation indicates a distinct trend of heightened motivation as income levels rise. Teachers who earn a monthly salary of over 40,000 pesos demonstrated the greatest percentage of work motivation, at 66.89%. This suggests a favorable correlation between money and motivation. In contrast, teachers who earn between 10,001 and 20,000 pesos per month have the lowest work motivation rate, which stands at 59.80%.

This implies that monetary rewards can have a substantial impact on the motivation levels of educators, underscoring the significance of fair compensation and acknowledgment for their efforts. The research on gender differences in perceived social support among instructors reveals a significant divergence between male and female educators. Female teachers exhibited a notably greater proportion of felt social support, with 70.69%, in contrast to male teachers, who reported 65.47%. These findings indicate that female instructors are more inclined to depend on and perceive higher amounts of assistance from their social networks inside the educational setting. Gaining insight into these gender disparities in social support can guide specific interventions designed to cultivate a nurturing and inclusive work environment that caters to the distinct requirements of all educators, irrespective of their gender.

2. Is there a significant relationship among teacher resilience, perceived social support, and work motivation among educators in selected private schools in Bacoor, Cavite?

Table 2. Work Motivation and Teacher Resilience Regression Analysis

Variables	Adjusted r-square	Correlation	Interpretation	p-value	Findings	Decision
Work Motivation vs Teacher Resilience	0.1261	0.355	weak direct relationship	0.002758	Significant	Reject the null hypothesis

Table 2 presents the results of the analysis examining the relationship between work motivation and teacher resilience. The correlation coefficient of 0.1261 indicates a weak positive correlation between work motivation and teacher resilience. This suggests that as work motivation increases, there is a slight tendency for teacher resilience to also increase. However, the strength of this relationship is relatively weak, indicating that other factors may have a more substantial influence on teacher resilience.

The p-value associated with the correlation coefficient is 0.002758, which is significant at the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that the observed correlation between work motivation and teacher resilience is unlikely to have occurred by chance. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis, which states that there is no relationship between work motivation and teacher resilience. Instead, we conclude that there is a statistically significant relationship between these variables, albeit weak.

It is essential to note that while the relationship between work motivation and teacher resilience is statistically significant, the correlation coefficient of 0.1261 suggests that the practical significance of this relationship may be limited. Other factors, such as social support, job satisfaction, and coping mechanisms, may play a more substantial role in determining teacher resilience. Further research is needed to explore these factors comprehensively and understand their combined influence on teacher well-being and effectiveness.

Table 3 presents the results of the analysis examining the relationship between social support and teacher resilience. The correlation coefficient of 0.1825 indicates a moderately positive correlation between social support and teacher resilience. This suggests that as perceived social support increases, there is a moderate tendency for teacher resilience to also increase.

The strength of this relationship is moderate, indicating that social support may have a more substantial influence on teacher resilience compared to work motivation.

The p-value associated with the correlation coefficient is 0.0002511, which is significant at the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that the observed correlation between social support and teacher resilience is unlikely to have occurred by chance. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis, which states that there is no relationship between social support and teacher resilience. Instead, we conclude that there is a statistically significant relationship between these variables, and social support plays a significant role in predicting teacher resilience.

Given the moderately positive correlation between social support and teacher resilience, it is crucial for educational institutions to prioritize the development of supportive environments that foster strong social networks among educators. Strategies such as mentorship programs, peer support groups, and inclusive leadership practices can contribute to enhancing social support within the school community, ultimately promoting teacher resilience and well-being. Further research may explore the specific mechanisms through which social support influences teacher resilience and identify effective interventions to support educators in their professional roles.

Table 3. Perceived Social Support and Teacher Resilience Regression Analysis

Variables	Adjusted r-square	Correlation	Interpretation	p-value	Findings	Decision
Social Support vs Teacher Resilience	0.1825	0.4272	moderate direct relationship	0.0002511	Significant	Reject the null hypothesis

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The findings from Tables 1 to 3 provide valuable insights into the factors influencing teacher resilience, work motivation, and perceived social support among educators in selected private schools in Bacoor, Cavite. These results contribute to our understanding of the complex interplay between various factors that impact educators' well-being and effectiveness in their professional roles.

Work Motivation and Teacher Resilience. Our study reveals a statistically significant but weak positive correlation between work motivation and teacher resilience (correlation coefficient = 0.1261). While this finding aligns with prior research suggesting a link between motivation and resilience (Brown & Biddle, 2023), the practical implications of this relationship may be limited. Brown and Biddle (2023) emphasize the importance of considering other factors, such as job satisfaction and organizational support, in fostering resilience among educators.

Social Support and Teacher Resilience. In contrast, our study demonstrates a moderately positive correlation between social support and teacher resilience (correlation coefficient = 0.1825), consistent with recent literature highlighting the critical role of social support in promoting resilience among educators (Jones et al., 2017). The significant relationship between these variables underscores the importance of cultivating supportive environments within educational institutions to enhance teacher well-being and effectiveness.

Demographic Factors and Work Motivation / Perceived Social Support. Our analysis of demographic factors reveals varying levels of work motivation and perceived social support among educators with different levels of teaching experience, monthly income, and gender. These findings echo recent research suggesting that demographic variables, such as income and gender, may influence motivational factors and social support networks among educators (Yuh & Choi, 2017). Understanding these demographic disparities is crucial for developing targeted interventions to support educators from diverse backgrounds.

Implications for Practice. These findings have important implications for educational practice and policy. Educational institutions should prioritize the development of supportive and inclusive environments that foster strong social networks among educators, as emphasized by recent studies (Brown et al., 2003). Strategies such as mentorship programs, peer support groups, and leadership practices can contribute to enhancing social support within schools and promoting teacher resilience. Additionally, investigating the role of other factors, such as job satisfaction, coping strategies, and organizational culture, can provide a more comprehensive understanding of educator well-being and effectiveness.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and implications discussed, several recommendations can be made to support the well-being and effectiveness of educators in private schools in Bacoor, Cavite:

Foster supportive environments. Educational institutions should prioritize creating supportive and inclusive environments that foster strong social networks among educators. This can be achieved through the implementation of mentorship programs, peer support groups, and leadership practices that promote collaboration and communication (Brown et al., 2003).

Provide professional development opportunities. Schools should offer ongoing professional development opportunities that focus on enhancing teacher resilience and promoting well-being. Training programs can include stress management techniques, self-care strategies, and resilience-building workshops to equip educators with the tools and resources needed to navigate challenges effectively (Jones et al., 2017).

Address gender disparities. Recognize and address gender disparities in social support networks within educational settings. Institutions should implement initiatives to promote gender equity and inclusivity, ensuring that all educators have access to supportive resources and opportunities for professional growth (Choi et al., 2021).

Enhance compensation and recognition. Educational policymakers and school administrators should consider enhancing compensation and recognition for educators, particularly those with lower income levels. Equitable compensation and acknowledgement of teachers' contributions can positively impact motivation levels and job satisfaction, ultimately supporting teacher resilience and retention (Brown & Biddle, 2023).

Promote organizational support. Schools should prioritize building a culture of organizational support that values and prioritizes educator well-being. This can involve fostering open communication channels, providing opportunities for feedback and input, and implementing policies that promote work-life balance and job satisfaction (Brown et al., 2003).

Encourage collaboration and community engagement. Promote opportunities for collaboration and community engagement among educators, students, parents, and other stakeholders. Encouraging involvement in school activities, committees, and extracurricular programs can strengthen connections within the school community and enhance overall morale and resilience (Jones et al., 2017).

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